

Assessment of Group Life Insurance Policy on Employees Performance in Federal Ministry of Works and Housing

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Abstract

The success or failure of any organization depends on how motivated its employees' are. Group life insurance is a subset of Employee benefit to improve their performance. The objective of the study is to determine the effect of group life insurance service on employees' performance in Federal Ministry of Works and Housing. The study adopted Principal Agent Theory Propounded by Jensen and Meckling 1976. The study adopted survey research design, primary method of data collection through questionnaires. With the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), Simple regression analysis was used to test the Hypothesis of the study. Findings from the study revealed that, there is a significant negative relationship between the group life insurance and employees' performance. The study rejects the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between group life insurance and employee's satisfaction in the Ministry of Work. The study recommended that the employer should educate the employees" of the benefits of the group life insurance policy and ensure that claims are paid promptly.

Keywords; Insurance, Group Life Insurance and Employee's Performance

Introduction

For any organization to attain its goals is dependent on several factors, one of the vital elements is human capital. The reality is that people influence important aspects of organizational performance in a multitude of ways. People conceive and implement the organizational strategy, while the mix of people and systems mostly determine an organization's capabilities. Competencies are required to execute the strategy, and these competencies are primarily a function of the skills and knowledge of an organization's human capital.

Therefore, the success of an organization is hinged upon how motivated its employees are (Lawler, 2003). Managers believe that employee benefit is a strong determinant of employees' performance and attitudes. Employee benefit is one of the strategies used in Human Resource Management for attracting and retaining useful employees as well as facilitating them to improve their performance. But at what level and mix is employee benefit most effective in determining level of performance.

Benefits according to Wright, Mondy, and Noe, [1996](#). (p. 356) '... include all financial rewards other than direct payment. Benefits cost the firm money, but employees usually receive them indirectly'. Employee benefits are virtually any form of compensation other than direct wages paid to employees (Rosenbloom, 2001,p,3), It constitute a major part of almost any individual's financial and economic security. Benefits are usually provided as a package of items, for example pensions, subsidized meals, insurance policy, discounts on company products and the like such benefits vary in importance to the individuals.

Taylor (1911) and Gilbreth (1868 – 1924) believed that employees don't like to work, therefore they have to be motivated in order to work. Organizations have been implementing employee benefit without knowledge of the relationship of such compensation mix with the employee performance. This study examines how group life insurance policy and affect employees' performance in.

Most empirical studies have asserted that employee benefit is a major booster for employees' performance looking at employee benefit as a whole (Ogah, Ade, & Ojo, 2013). This study however intends to look at a subset of employees' group life insurance. This study intends to examine how group life insurance policy affects employees' performance in Federal Ministry of Works and Housing.

Objectives of the Study

To determine the effect of group life insurance service on employees' performance in Federal Ministry of Works and Housing.

Hypotheses

H0: Group life insurance service has no significant effect on employees' performance in Federal Ministry of Works and Housing.

Conceptual Framework Insurance

It is important to note that there is no single definition for the term insurance, it is given different definition by various researchers depending on the angle from which they see it. But the clear thing we can see from the definitions is that they all have a common idea which is "insurance gives protection against losses" or "it transfers the risk of one person or a party to another" or it spread the risk of one person or a group of people among several people.

Also, insurance is said to be protection against possible financial loss. Despite the fact that there are different types of insurance, they all have a similarity; they give peace of mind this is as a result of the assurance that money will be available to meet the needs of your survivors, pay your medical bills, protect your personal belongings and cover personal property damage (Kapoor, Dlabay and Hughes 2001:311 cited by Tripathy and Pal, 2005).

There are many variants of life insurance contracts. Some contracts including term and whole life are used exclusively or primarily to provide protection against premature death. Others such as endowment and universal life combine protection against premature death with a type of savings vehicle. Term insurance provides protection for a fixed term (e.g., 1, 5, or 15 years). If death occurs during the policy's term, a fixed amount is paid to the beneficiary. There are no other benefits or cash value build-up. Whole life – provides for the payment of the face value of the policy upon death of the insured, regardless of when it may occur and Group Life insurance.

Group Life Insurance

This insurance covers a large number of insured a person under a single policy. By purchasing group life insurance policy coverage through an insurance provider on a wholesale basis for its members, companies are able to secure costs for each individual employee that are much lower than if they purchase it individually.

Those receiving group life insurance coverage may not have to pay anything out of pocket for policy benefits. Anyone who chooses to take more advanced coverage may elect to have their portion of the premium payment deducted from their paycheck. Just like regular insurance policies, insured parties are required to list one or more beneficiaries before the policy comes into effect. Beneficiaries can be changed at any point during the coverage period.

With group life insurance, the employer or organization purchasing the policy for its staff or members retains the master contract. Employees who elect coverage through the group policy usually receive a certificate of coverage which is needed to provide to a subsequent insurance company in the event that the individual leaves the company or organization and terminates their coverage.

Group life insurance is offered by employers as a benefit for its staff, it has a relatively low coverage amount and is typically offered as a piece of a larger employer or membership benefit package(Kagan, 2019).

Employee Performance

Employee performance is about employees achieving the results, goals or standards as per the expectations set by the organisation. Employees are rated on how well they do their jobs compared to the performance standards set. In short, it is the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed, the initiatives they take, their creativity in solving problems and the resourcefulness in the way they utilise their resources, time and energy (Rothman, Coetzer, 2003).

Employee performance involves factors such as quality, quantity and effectiveness of work as well as the behaviors your employees show in the workplace. Measuring performance is of great importance to an incentive plan because it communicates the importance of established organizational goals. "What gets measured and rewarded gets attention" (Bohlander, Snell, Sherman, 2001). In discipline of human resource management, different writers suggest the following indicators for measuring employee performance and they include: quality that can be measured by percentage of work output that must be redone or is rejected; Customer satisfaction that can be measured by the number of customers and customer feedback. Also, timeliness, measured in terms of how fast work is performed by the employee when given a certain task; absenteeism/tardiness observed when employees absent themselves from work; and achievement of objectives measured when an employee has surpassed his/her set targets, he/she is then considered to have performed well to achieve objectives (Hakala, 2008; Armstrong, 2006). Performance can as well be measured by the various methods of performance appraisal including Management by Objectives (MBOs), Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scales (BARS), Assessment Centers, and Cost Accounting Method among the modern ones.

Empirical Review Life Insurance Policy and Employees Performance

Liebenberg and Sommer (2016) developed and tested a model that explains insurers' performance as a function of line-of-business diversification and other variables using a sample of property-liability insurers over the period 1995-2004. The results indicate that undiversified insurers consistently outperform diversified insurers. In terms of accounting performance, the diversification penalty is at least 1 percent of return on assets or 2 percent of return on equity. Using a market-based performance measure (Tobin's Q) the authors find that the market applies a significant discount to diversified insurers. The existence of a diversification penalty (and diversification discount) provides strong support for the strategic focus hypothesis. The authors also find that insurance groups underperform unaffiliated insurers and that stock insurers outperform mutuals.

Gohari, Ahmadloo, Boroujeni and Hosseinipour (2013) studied the relationship between insurance and employee performance in two Malaysian Tourism Companies using backward multiple regression technique. The data was collected from 77 employees using questionnaire, the study concluding that although all insurance policy types have a direct positive relationship with employee performance, based on correlation test intrinsic types lose their importance when they are considered in a more comprehensive model including other forms of insurance policy. They recommended further studies on insurance variables since they are numerous.

Gunu (2010) studied the influence of insurance on the individual Performance of Sales Representatives of Pharmaceutical Companies based in Ilorin Nigeria, as well as the type of insurance that elicit greater performance among sales people. The study employed Convenience sampling design to select the sample size and questionnaire was used as primary data collection tool. The research findings were that there was a significant relationship between insurance and performance.

Ogah, Ade, and Ojo (2013) in their study Effects of life insurance policy on employee performance using correlation research design, examined 84 employees of Nigeria power and Lightning Company Limited, observing that life insurance policy had no significant relationship with performance. Those receiving life insurance policy and those not receiving performed the same. It was perceived that life insurance policy have a significant influence in motivating employees to perform however the relationship was significant only when it comes to attendance. The researchers recommended that organizations should strive to understand their employees in developing and making the life insurance policy systems easier to assess as there is no perfect system. Methodology

Theoretical Framework Principal Agent Theory Propounded by Jensen and Meckling

An agency relationship can be presented as any employment relationship wherein one party (the principal) depends on another party (the agent) to undertake an action on behalf of the latter. The formal agency literature presents two different but related models. The first one focuses on precontractual and the second on post-contractual issues. There is also a positive branch within the theory, mainly concerning the design of appropriate intra-organizational control mechanisms and governance. Agency theory uses the contract to describe the relationships in which one party delegates work to another (Jensen and Meckling 1976). The focus of the theory is on determining the most efficient contract in an exchange relationship in order to govern it, given the characteristics of the parties involved, and considering the fact that the cost of obtaining information and environmental

uncertainty in business relationships make it impossible for the principal to monitor the agent completely. It is important to realize that most agency models define efficiency from the principal's point of view. The main assumption is that the principal is the dominant party in the relationship. Hence, rather than maximizing the benefits for both the principal and the agent, the 'efficient' contract ensures the best possible outcome for the principal, given the constraints imposed by the situation (Bergen, Dutta, and Walker Jr 1992).

Two Types of Agency Problems, when the principal forges a relationship with an agent, it faces two distinct problems. The first one pre-contractual problem arises when the principal decides to offer an agent a contract. The major issue here is deciding on the strategy to find an agent who has the characteristics the principal seeks. The second problem emerges after the principal and the agent have forged the relationship. It is called a 'post-contractual problem'. The major issue here is to decide on the information strategy that the principal should employ to evaluate and reward the agent's performance to guarantee that he/she will be motivated to behave in a manner consistent with the principal's goals. Precontractual issues are often termed as 'hidden information' problems and post-contractual issues as 'hidden action' problems (Bergen, Dutta, and Walker Jr 1992).

Methodology

The research design for the study is survey. This study collected data from the staff of the Federal Ministry of Works thus making a survey effective in executing the research. The study established the assessment of employee's satisfaction in the life insurance transactions in the Federal ministry of works which was collected using questionnaires. The factors was be tabulated in the questionnaires and expressed using relative frequencies.

The population for this study is the entire staff of the ministry which according to the human resource management study is 1307.

Taro Yamane

Formula $n =$

N

$$1 + N(e)^2$$

Where n =sample size

N =total population size e = the assume error margin or tolerable error which is taken as 5% (0.05)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{1307}{1 + 1307(0.05)^2} = \frac{1307}{3.27} = \underline{\underline{400}}$$

Sample size = 400

Stratified Sampling Method

N

----- * S

P

N - Is the number of elements in the stratum

P - Is the population of the study

S - Is the required sample size

Table 1: Sample Stratification

S/No	Department	Population	Sample Strata
1.	Highway planning and development	77	24
2.	Highway design and bridge	78	24
3.	Highway construction and rehabilitation	120	37
4.	Highway materials	90	28
5.	Geo technical and quality control	110	35
6.	Engineering department/service (ES)	260	80
7.	Planning research and statistic	58	17
8.	Human resources management	65	21
9.	Finance and accounts	32	9
10.	Public procurement	70	21
11.	Reform coordinator and service improvement	77	24
12.	Public private partnership	110	35
13.	Department of Legal Services	38	11
14.	Internal audit	24	7
15.	Press and public relation	31	9
16.	Anti-corruption and transparency	42	12
17.	Servicom department	25	7
	Total	1307	400

Source: Researchers computation 2020

Source of Data

The study adopted primary method of data collection, questionnaire were administered and Simple regression used to analysed the data through the aid of SPSS software.

$$\text{Emp} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LIFE} + e \dots \dots \dots \text{eq (i)}$$

Where: Emp = Employee's performance

B_0 = is the constant or coefficient of intercept.

LIFE = Group life insurance

Table 2: Number of questionnaires distributed and how many retrieved. **Respondents Response Rate Percentage (%)** Returned 320 80 Unreturned 80 20 Total 400 100 Source: Field Survey 2019

The Table 2 shows that out of 400 questionnaires administered to the staff of the ministry of works, only 320 representing 80% were completed and returned, while 80 questionnaires representing 20% of the questionnaires were not returned. The 320 returned questionnaires were used for the analysis.

Table 3: Variables Entered/Removed ^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	GROUP LIFE INSURANCE ^b		. Enter

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 3 shows summary of the variables entered in the SPSS package, which are one dependent variable which is employee's performance and one independent variable group life insurance.

Table 4: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.772 ^a	.596	.595	.7045	2.01

- a. Predictors: (Constant), GROUP LIFE INSURANCE
- b. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE'S SATISFACTION

Table 4 showed the summary of the model in the study and explained the coefficient of correlation depicted by R, which is 0.772. It also reported the coefficient of determination depicted by R², which is equal to 0.596. AdjustedR² which is 0.595. A standard error of 0.7045 and Durbin Watson statistic of 2.1 were also reported accordingly.

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	232.983	1	232.983	469.469	.000 ^b
	Residual	157.814	318	.496		
	Total	390.797	319			

- a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE
- b. Predictors: (Constant), GROUP LIFE INSURANCE

Table 5 showed the overall analysis of variance (ANOVA), which showed the breakdown of the regression result into its components of Sum of square and mean of square. It showed overall, b whether the model is fit to describe the data or not. This is evidence in the value of the F statistic of 469.469 and the significant column depicted as sig 000.

Table 6: Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.375	.165		1.062	.289
	GROUP LIFE INSURANCE	-.912	.042	.772	21.667	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE'S PRFORMANCE

Table 6 showed the coefficient of the independent variables and it respective significant. As shown in the result table, B0, which represents the constant term has a value of 0.375, B1, which is the coefficient of group life insurance by X1 has a value of -0.912 Also, the significance of these values as shown on the **Sig** column are 0.000

Discussion of Findings

The coefficient of determination (R^2), with value of 0.722 suggest that 72% of the variation that occurs in the dependent variable-employees' performance of workers is explained by the independent variables- group life insurance while 28% is explained by other external variables, which are not included in the model. This means that group life insurance strongly explains employees' performance in Federal Ministry of Works and Housing. The Durbin Watson statistic value of 2.1 is strong indication of the absence of any serious auto or serial correlation, meaning that the error terms are not in any way correlated. We are therefore confident that we have obtained a non-spurious or nonsense regression results in the analysis.

Furthermore, the analysis of variance result is highly significant as the calculated statistic is less than the 5% α level of significant. As in below, starting from the contribution of group life insurance, which has a coefficient value of -0.912 and a significant value of 0.000, which is less than the 5% is an indication that we can reject the null hypothesis of non-significant relationship between group life insurance and employees' satisfaction in Federal ministry of Works and Housing. Therefore, group life insurance policy significantly affects employees' performance in Federal ministry of Works and Housing. This finding align with the study of Gohari, Ahmadloo, Boroujeni and Hosseinipour (2013).

Conclusion and Recommendations

In view of the fact that the regression result is significant at 5%, we conclude that the findings is statistically reliable for conclusion to be derived. Also, the result can be taken to be unbiased and nonspurious. We are confident to reject the hypothesis which states that there is no relationship between group life insurance and employees' performance in ministry of work and Housing that though there is relationship between the two variables, but such relationship is in a negative form and not favorable to the employees' in the ministry. This may find may imply that employees of Federal ministry of Works and Housing consider the group life insurance policy a lip service by their employer and that they are not genuinely about the intention of the group life insurance policy probably claims are not paid or not paid on time. Therefore, the study recommends that:

Life insurance is a way of dealing with risk and a saving medium for consumers. It also plays important psychological and social roles. The major function of life insurance is to protect against financial loss from loss of human life and as such the employers of staff at Federal Ministry of Works and Housing should educate the workers on the benefits of group life insurance and ensure that employees' claims should be paid promptly without hassles.

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